

Article

Fly Ash and Bottom Ash from Biomass and Coal: Comparison of Properties in Grate and Fluidized Bed Combustion from the Perspective of Construction Applications

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Abstract

The cement industry seeks alternative raw materials to lower its environmental impact, and biomass ash represents a potential material for construction applications. This study evaluates biomass ashes (BMA) produced from grate and fluidized bed combustion, as well as co-combustion with coal, focusing on their chemical, mineralogical, and physical characteristics. The results reveal a substantial variability in BMA composition, influenced primarily by the fuel type and combustion method. This heterogeneity critically affects the reactivity and overall suitability of the BMA for use in construction materials. It was found that none of the 23 analyzed samples met the requirements of EN 450-1. This outcome is largely attributable to the combustion process and to sampling from the bottom part of the boiler, which typically yields material with properties outside the limits of the standard. Even when assessed directly against the specific limit values of EN 450-1, the ashes did not comply without further processing or modification. Despite these limitations, BMA show potential for use in accordance with EN 197-1, which permits the incorporation of up to 5 wt.% minor additional constituents. However, their practical application under this framework requires validation through tests performed on hydrated cement. These findings underline both the limitations and the promise of BMA as a supplementary cementitious material (SCMs) in sustainable construction.

Keywords: biomass ash; supplementary cementitious materials; co-combustion; grate combustion; fluidized bed combustion; chemical composition; phase composition

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1. Introduction

The cement industry is one of the largest emitters of carbon dioxide in the world. The production of one ton of Portland cement accounts for approximately 0.5–0.9 tons of CO₂ emissions [1–3], with this sector contributing to 5–8% of global anthropogenic emissions [3,4]. Emissions originate both from the chemical process of limestone calcination, during which CO₂ is released, and from the combustion of fuels required to reach kiln temperatures of approximately 1450 °C [2,5]. Furthermore, cement consumption remains exceptionally high and continues to rise due to the global demand for concrete, which

further increases the environmental burden [1,5]. Nowadays, the growing demand for scarce resources, coupled with the need to reduce CO₂ emissions, is becoming a major challenge for the construction industry [6]. One approach to lowering the carbon footprint of cement is the partial substitution of Portland clinker with supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) such as silica fume, fly ash (FA), slag, etc. [1,6,7].

One of the most common SCMs is FA from pulverized coal combustion (PCC), which originates during the combustion of pulverized coal in power plants as a fine powdery material captured in electrostatic or mechanical separators [8–10]. FA has beneficial effects on the properties of concrete, including enhanced workability of fresh mixes, reduced hydration heat, improved long-term strength and durability, and lower permeability [1,11]. From an environmental perspective, its use decreases the volume of waste directed to landfills, lowers Portland cement consumption, and thus reduces CO₂ emissions [1,4,5,11]. Another by-product of coal combustion is bottom ash (BA), which accumulates at the bottom of the boiler. In contrast to fly ash, it exhibits a coarser fraction, a lower specific surface area, and a distinct mineralogical composition. Due to its lower pozzolanic activity, it is used to a limited extent, most typically in road construction, or is deposited in landfills [8,10].

In addition to fly ash and bottom ash generated by PCC, fluidized bed combustion (FBC) technology is also used in the energy sector. FBC allows fuels of varying quality, including biomass, to be burned at relatively low temperatures of 700–950 °C [10,12–14]. FBC fly ash differs from standard FA in the irregular shape of its particles [12,13]. During FBC, flue gas desulfurization is often performed directly in the boiler through the addition of ground limestone or dolomite. The reaction of CaCO₃ with SO_x leads to the formation of sulfates, which remain in the fly ash [9,10,12,14]. At the same time, the desulfurization process is the reason for the possible presence of free lime (CaO) [9,10,12–14]. This method of flue gas desulfurization affects the chemical composition and properties of FBC ashes, particularly their sulfate and free lime content, which must be considered when using them in cement production. These differences can lead to undesirable volume changes and the faster hydration of cement, which limits its use as an SCM.

Ash not used in industry is usually stored in landfills or dumps. This poses not only environmental risks (groundwater pollution, dust), but also the loss of potentially valuable material [1,4,5,11]. The use of ashes as SCMs therefore offers two advantages: it decreases waste generation and contributes to lowering the carbon footprint of cement.

There are a number of other SCMs; the most important include blast furnace slag, calcined clays, metakaolin, construction and demolition waste, or ash from various types of biomass combustion [1,5,6,11]. Biomass is generally defined as material composed wholly or partially of plant-based matter originating from agricultural or forestry sources, which is burned to obtain energy [15]. Wood biomass includes all trees and woody plants, including branches, which are not suitable for commercial use [15]. In addition to wood biomass, agricultural residues such as corn stalks and herbaceous biomass also exhibit promising potential [15,16]. The most common materials include wood, bark, wood chips, corn straw, rapeseed straw, olive pomace, olive pits, açai seed, rice husk, sugarcane stalks and herbaceous biomass [17–19]. The use of biomass as a renewable energy source in the energy sector is an innovative process, not only for economic and technological reasons, but especially in the context of sustainable environmental development [16]. Biomass is considered a carbon-neutral type of fuel because the CO₂ emitted as a result of its combustion corresponds to the amount previously absorbed by plants from the atmosphere [16].

Biomass can be combusted in several ways, the most common of which are grate combustion and FBC. Grate combustion is a traditional technology used mainly in small- and medium-sized boilers [14]. The fuel is distributed evenly on a moving or fixed grate, and the combustion takes place with air supplied from below. Typical temperatures for

the grate combustion are 1000–1200 °C, and the resulting ash accumulates on the grate (BA) or is carried away as FA [14]. FBC is an advanced technology that enables the efficient utilization of a wide range of fuels, including mixtures of coal and biomass [14]. FBC takes place at relatively low temperatures (700–900 °C), which limits NO_x formation and the risk of ash sintering [14].

From an environmental perspective, the reuse of biomass ash has several benefits, such as reducing CO₂ emissions associated with cement production, conserving natural resources, and solving the problem of waste disposal [20] through its use in concrete or as a mineral additive [20]. Wang et al., 2025 [21], investigated the use of wood ash for construction purposes, but found that its application in concrete and mortar is limited by a significant variability in chemical composition and physical properties, processing technology, and the absence of clear standards, which complicate its reliable and wide use in practice. Carević et al., 2020 [22], used wood BMA as a partial substitute for cement. In this case, too, special attention must be paid to chemical and physical properties. According to the authors, 10% is required for an acceptable substitute; a higher substitute would require further modifications such as sieving and/or washing with water. Hu et al., 2025 [23], investigated the co-combustion of biomass (corn straw) with coal and monitored the ability of alkali metals and alkaline earth metals in biomass to be fixed into the aluminosilicate–phosphate matrix of coal ash, which leads to the formation of eutectics. Putra et al., 2024 [24], monitored the properties of ash from non-wood biomass (spelt husk, oat husk, hay) and its pozzolanic reactivity, finding that ash from spelt husk showed the greatest potential. At the same time, it was demonstrated that the addition of kaolinite (1 wt.%) to biomass stabilizes the amorphous phase at higher combustion temperatures and increases the reactivity of the resulting ash. In general, the use of BMA fly ash is limited by legislative requirements and the variability of its composition. Legislation (EN 450-1) allows its use in concrete only if it is co-combusted with coal and only in the form of fly ash, as bottom ash is not covered by this standard [25,26]. Another option is to use biomass ash as a minor additional constituent in blended cements in accordance with EN 197-1, up to a maximum of 5% by weight [27]. An obstacle to wider use is the instability of its composition and high content of alkalis and chlorides, which can negatively affect the long-term durability of concrete [25,26]. The use of biomass ash is therefore conditioned by its chemical and mineralogical composition, physical properties, type of combustion technology, and method of ash handling [26]. That is why research focuses mainly on ash from the co-combustion of coal and biomass, which is legislatively accepted, while ash from pure biomass remains largely unused waste in many countries [4,20,26]. Compared to coal ash, biomass ash has a lower content of aluminum, silicon, iron, and sulfur and a higher content of calcium, chlorides, potassium, magnesium, sodium, oxygen, and phosphorus [16,28–30]. In terms of phase composition, it contains compounds such as alkali silicates and carbonates, and potassium–sodium chlorides [16]. The chemical and phase composition of biomass ash depends on the characteristics of the biomass, combustion parameters, the proportion of individual plant components, and other factors, such as grain size and the type of soil in which the plant grew [16,31]. Ashes from rice husks, rice straw, and other agricultural residues are rich in silicon dioxide (SiO₂) [28,32,33]. Phosphorus pentoxide (P₂O₅) is most abundant in ashes from animal-derived materials, especially bone meal [28]. Notable amounts of P₂O₅ are also present in ashes from algae, agricultural residues, and certain energy crops [28,34]. Wood biomass (bark, wood chips, etc.) has calcium oxide (CaO) as its main component [28,29,35–37], while other sources rich in CaO are hay and straw [29,38,39]. Cereal straw and herbaceous biomass materials are also rich in potassium-bearing (K⁺) and chloride-bearing (Cl[−]) phases [40]. Furthermore, chlorides are present in elevated concentrations in animal waste [28,29].

The aim of this work is to observe and compare the chemical, mineralogical, and selected physical properties of ashes produced by different combustion methods (grate combustion and FBC) and from different types of fuels (bark, hay and straw, wood chips, sawdust and coal), both for FA and BA or their combinations. The samples originated from various locations in the Czech Republic with different input fuel compositions. The novelty of this study lies in expanding the existing data base across combustion technologies and fuel types and in clearly demonstrating the substantial variability in the composition and reactivity of biomass ashes, including materials produced within the same combustion units, which is essential for a realistic assessment of their applicability not only as SCMs in cement, but also for other potential uses. The findings of this work should support the more effective utilization of these materials in construction industry practice.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sampling

Ash samples collected between 2021 and 2024 at six locations in the Czech Republic were selected as input materials for the analyses. These locations represent different types of combustion technologies—grate combustion of biomass, grate co-combustion of biomass with coal, and fluidized co-combustion of coal with biomass. The materials incinerated were bark, mixtures of hay and straw, wood chips, sawdust, and coal. The resulting products were bottom ash (BA) and fly ash (FA) or a combination of both (FA+BA). Three representative samples were selected from each location according to the type of resulting ash. A total of 23 samples were analyzed, whose specifications are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of input raw materials.

Label	Sample No.	Method of Combustion	Combusted Material	Type of Ash	Location
LBP_FA LBP_BA	1, 2, 3 1, 2, 3	Grate combustion	Wood bark	FA BA	Lenzing Biocel Paskov a.s (LBP) (Paskov, CZ)
JH_FA+BA	1, 2, 3	Grate combustion	Hay and straw	FA+BA	Energetické centrum s.r.o. (JH) (Jindřichův Hradec, CZ)
CZTL_BA	1	Grate co-combustion	Woodchips + coal	BA	CZT Litoměřice (CZTL) (Litoměřice, CZ)
CZTM_BA	1	Grate co-combustion	Woodchips and sawdust + coal	BA	CZT Mimoň (CZTM) (Mimoň, CZ)
HO_FA HO_BA	1, 2, 3 1, 2, 3	FBC co-combustion	80% coal + 20% woodchips + wood bark + forest biomass residues	FA BA	Power plant Hodonín (HO) (Hodonín, CZ)
PO_FA PO_BA	1, 2, 3 1, 2, 3	FBC co-combustion	80% coal + 20% woodchips	FA BA	Power plant Poříčí (PO) (Trutnov, CZ)

2.2. Methods

The chemical composition was determined through X-ray fluorescence analysis (XRF) using a sequential wavelength-dispersive X-ray spectrometer PERFORM'X (Thermo ARL, Ecublens, Switzerland). All element spectral line intensities were measured in vacuum using the Oxsas 2.7.1.5587 program. The generator–collimator–crystal–detector settings were optimized for 83 measured elements with a time of 6 s per element. The obtained intensities were processed using the integrated Uniquant 5 program without the need to measure standards. All samples for XRF were pre-homogenized and manually ground in an agate mortar.

The loss on ignition (LOI) was determined according to the standard EN 196-2 [41] and was performed by firing the samples in a muffle furnace at 950 ± 25 °C for 1 h with repeated firing until constant weight. Each sample was tested three times.

The phase composition (XRD) was determined on an Empyrean diffractometer with a Cu anode ($\lambda K\alpha = 1.54184$ Å) (Malvern Panalytical, Almelo, The Netherlands). The results were evaluated using HighScore Plus 3.1 software. The amorphous content (quantitative phase analysis) was determined using the internal standard method (20 wt.% CaF₂, was added to the samples). All samples for XRD were pre-homogenized and manually ground in an agate mortar.

Density was determined using a helium pycnometer Pycnomatic ATC Evo (Microtrac, Haan/Düsseldorf, Germany). Specific surfaces were measured using an electronic Blaine device (Testing, Berlin, Germany) according to the standard EN 196-6 [42].

Particle size distribution (PSD) was measured on a laser particle size analyzer Better-sizer ST (Bettersize Instruments, Dandong, China) with a range of 0–1000 µm.

Microscopic methods included the use of a scanning electron microscope (SEM) LYRA3 with a FEG electron gun (Tescan, Brno, Czech Republic) at acceleration voltage of 10 kV by detection of BSE (back-scattered electrons). Elemental analyses were performed using an energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analyzer with a 80 mm² SDD detector X-MaxN (Oxford Instruments, High Wycombe, UK) and AZtecEnergy software (AZtec 3.3 SP1) (Oxford Instruments, High Wycombe, UK).

2.3. EN 450-1 Requirements

The suitability of the ashes as SCM is verified if the requirements specified in EN 450-1: Fly ash for concrete—part 1: Definition, specification and conformity criteria [25] are met. The requirements concern the chemical composition, free lime content, and loss on ignition. The evaluation criteria are provided in Table 2. These criteria apply to fly ash obtained from the combustion of pulverized coal or coal co-combusted with additional materials and collected from flue gases by electrostatic or mechanical dust separators, as defined in EN 450-1. From the perspective of EN 450-1, the biomass ashes supplied for this study do not meet the fundamental definition of fly ash, as they were neither generated under pulverized coal combustion conditions nor collected from flue gases by electrostatic or mechanical dust separators. Nevertheless, this standard can still serve as a useful reference framework for assessing the properties of biomass ash and evaluating its potential applicability in construction materials.

Table 2. Evaluation criteria for the suitability of ashes by EN 450-1.

Evaluated Parameter	Limit Value [wt.%]
Chloride (Cl ⁻)	<0.10
Sulfur trioxide (SO ₃)	<3
Magnesium oxide (MgO)	<4
Phosphorus pentoxide (P ₂ O ₅)	<5
Free lime (CaO)	<1.5
Active calcium oxide (CaO)	<10
Active silicon dioxide (SiO ₂)	>25
Silicon dioxide (SiO ₂) + aluminium oxide (Al ₂ O ₃) + iron(III) oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	>70
Alkali (Na ₂ O _{eq})	<5
	<5 category A
Loss on ignition	<7 category B
	<9 category C

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Chemical Composition (XRF)

Figures 1–3 and Table 3 show that the chemical composition of the materials varies, while all are rich in silicon dioxide (SiO_2), aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3), iron oxide (Fe_2O_3), and calcium oxide (CaO). All subsequent evaluations of chemical composition in this section are performed solely with respect to the limits defined in EN 450-1, which are used here exclusively as a reference benchmark reflecting the current practice for assessing fly ash intended for use in cementitious systems.

Figure 1. Chemical composition of input materials from grate combustion from XRF in wt.%.

Figure 2. Chemical composition of input materials from grate co-combustion from XRF in wt.%.

The SiO_2 content of the samples ranges widely from 7.36 to 68.93 wt.%. The fly ash samples LBP_FA_1-3 and the bottom ash sample LBP_BA_1 from grate combustion do not meet the reference requirement of at least 25 wt.% silicon dioxide content. The Al_2O_3 content ranges from 1.14 to 34.40 wt.%, and the Fe_2O_3 content ranges from 0.58 to 10.73 wt.%. Within the referential framework, the commonly applied criterion that requires more than 70 wt.% $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ is not met by most samples, regardless of combustion type. The amount of alkali $\text{Na}_2\text{O}_{\text{eq}}$ ranges from 0.38 wt.% to 18.47 wt.%, which, for some samples, does not meet the commonly referenced requirement for the total amount of alkalis, which should be less than 5 wt.%. The samples that did not meet this parameter were LBP_FA_1-3, JH_FA+BA_1-3, and one sample HO_BA_1. Only samples from the locations JH, CZTL, and CZTM met the reference limit for CaO content; the other samples exhibited a content higher than 10 wt.%, again relative to commonly used evaluation criteria. The reference MgO limit (<4 wt.%) was exceeded by samples LBP_FA_1-3, LBP_BA_1-3, HO_FA_1 and HO_FA_3, and the SO_3 benchmark limit (3 wt.%) was met only by samples from co-combustion biomass with coal (woodchips + wood bark + forest biomass residues). Similarly, the

majority of samples did not meet the reference chloride content limit (0.1 wt.%). In contrast, only two samples JH FA+BA_2 and JH FA+BA_3 failed to meet the limit for P₂O₅ (<5 wt.%).

Figure 3. Chemical composition of input materials from FBC co-combustion from XRF in wt.%

Table 3. Chemical composition of input materials from XRF in wt.%. Values marked in red do not comply with the EN 450–1 standard.

Sample	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	MgO	CaO	TiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	Cl ⁻	Others	SAF *	Na ₂ O _{eq} **
LBP_FA_1	5.29	18.60	3.45	0.66	8.17	9.75	34.09	0.48	2.82	12.49	0.32	3.88	27.34	6.03
LBP_FA_2	3.68	13.63	3.05	0.93	9.16	9.31	38.24	0.42	2.95	13.82	0.36	4.44	20.36	6.96
LBP_FA_3	6.55	22.95	3.86	0.79	6.67	13.49	26.43	0.52	2.26	13.29	0.16	3.03	33.36	5.18
LBP_BA_1	2.01	7.36	3.68	0.00	0.59	50.59	17.88	0.12	2.48	11.26	0.02	4.02	13.05	0.38
LBP_BA_2	7.27	27.79	10.68	0.43	1.72	17.97	17.30	0.51	2.54	10.27	0.03	3.49	45.74	1.56
LBP_BA_3	19.91	36.90	8.76	0.72	2.53	12.31	4.87	1.03	1.58	10.14	0.06	1.19	65.57	2.38
JH_FA+BA_1	1.63	57.22	1.00	0.31	16.90	2.42	8.79	0.13	4.70	2.48	4.10	0.33	59.85	11.43
JH_FA+BA_2	2.90	41.50	1.36	0.75	26.92	2.66	8.55	0.21	5.47	3.67	5.52	0.48	45.76	18.47
JH_FA+BA_3	1.14	42.47	0.58	0.37	26.79	2.81	9.44	0.08	5.62	5.32	4.95	0.43	44.19	17.99
CZTL_BA_1	34.40	42.38	7.88	0.66	0.77	1.35	3.86	6.03	0.49	1.21	0.00	0.97	84.66	1.17
CZTM_BA_1	33.80	40.25	7.01	2.39	0.63	2.18	4.38	6.04	0.58	1.84	0.01	0.89	81.06	2.80
HO_FA_1	8.07	29.68	3.45	0.80	6.06	4.96	36.08	0.68	3.34	4.21	0.48	2.19	41.20	4.79
HO_FA_2	16.36	34.72	4.12	0.80	3.47	2.90	26.82	1.07	1.81	6.51	0.16	1.26	55.20	3.08
HO_FA_3	11.26	41.83	4.96	1.18	5.17	4.47	23.37	0.76	2.61	2.85	0.39	1.15	58.05	4.58
HO_BA_1	6.87	55.11	1.88	0.94	9.02	2.69	19.04	0.31	2.03	0.37	0.02	1.73	63.86	6.87
HO_BA_2	10.72	25.98	10.73	0.33	1.40	1.47	36.17	0.77	0.49	11.41	0.01	0.53	47.43	1.25
HO_BA_3	8.08	68.48	2.07	1.03	3.87	2.65	10.94	0.32	1.48	0.48	0.11	0.49	78.63	3.58
PO_FA_1	10.38	45.54	4.08	1.25	5.63	3.39	21.21	0.78	2.64	2.77	0.39	1.94	60.00	4.95
PO_FA_2	28.67	41.15	5.49	0.59	1.16	1.68	14.88	1.76	0.41	3.76	0.01	0.44	75.31	1.36
PO_FA_3	10.25	42.49	3.69	0.92	5.90	3.59	24.18	0.71	3.44	2.92	0.29	1.62	56.43	4.81
PO_BA_1	7.41	68.55	2.13	0.68	4.09	2.35	11.52	0.39	1.55	0.26	0.00	1.08	78.09	3.37
PO_BA_2	16.57	27.65	3.05	0.37	0.90	1.20	36.24	1.17	0.31	12.23	0.00	0.31	47.27	0.96
PO_BA_3	6.43	68.93	1.67	0.53	4.26	1.86	12.75	0.28	2.05	0.37	0.01	0.86	77.03	3.33

* SAF = Σ SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃; ** the content of alkalis Na₂O_{eq} (=Na₂O + 0.658 K₂O).

The results show that the most frequently exceeded benchmark limits were those for sulphates (SO₃), chlorides (Cl⁻) and CaO, regardless of the type of combustion. In some samples, the values for MgO (locations LBP, HO) and alkalis (locations LBP, JH and HO) also exceeded the benchmark limits, especially in samples from the grate combustion of

pure biomass (wood bark, hay + straw). Samples from the location JH showed a high potassium content, which corresponds to the findings of Hernández Allica et al., 2001 [40], who also report the chemical composition of straw ash with a high potassium content.

Considering combustion technology, the samples exhibited significant differences. Ash from the grate combustion of pure biomass (wood bark, hay + straw; locations LBP, JH) did not meet the reference requirements of the standard for any evaluated parameter. The samples from FBC co-combustion (locations HO, PO) exhibited a higher compliance with the reference requirements of the standard, although slightly above-limit values were recorded, especially for SO_3 , CaO, chlorides, and alkalis. The samples from grate co-combustion (CZTL, CZTM) showed a very favorable chemical composition relative to these reference criteria.

Only two samples—CZTL and CZTM—fully aligned with all reference limits; both were produced through the grate co-combustion of woodchips with coal or woodchips and sawdust with coal. The advantage of this combustion in terms of the resulting ash composition is the fact that, in these two samples, flue gas desulfurization takes place behind the boiler. The other samples deviated from the reference limits in at least one parameter. A significant non-compliance with the reference standard is the high content of CaO in the samples. The source of CaO in fly ash is both the biomass itself and the flue gas desulfurization process associated with the addition of limestone, often in excess [10,43–46]. This fact subsequently affects the representation of other components, especially the low total amount of $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$. Along with CaO, a higher amount of MgO also appears in the ash samples. The highest MgO content—50.59 wt.%—was observed in sample LBP_BA_1; however, this value is highly atypical, and no satisfactory explanation for it could be identified. The highest content of chlorides, P_2O_5 , and alkalis was noted for ash from Jindřichův Hradec (JH), which was produced purely from biomass (hay + straw) without co-firing with coal.

3.2. Loss on Ignition (LOI)

In terms of LOI (Table 4), the best results were achieved by samples from FBC (locations HO, PO). Most of them met the limit values when evaluated against the EN 450-1 reference framework, which confirms their high combustion efficiency and suitability for further use. On the contrary, samples from the grate combustion of pure biomass (wood bark, hay + straw; locations LBP, JH) showed very high LOI values (up to 25 wt.%), which indicates an insufficient combustion and places them outside the reference limits typically used for evaluating fly ash quality. Even samples from grate co-combustion (CZTL, CZTM) had an LOI significantly above the category C reference limit value. The lowest values of LOI below 2 wt.% were observed in bottom ashes LBP_BA_3 (LOI 1.89 wt.%), HO_BA_1 (LOI 0.42 wt.%), and PO_BA_1 (LOI 0.35 wt.%). No correlations were identified between composition, ash type, or origin and LOI, owing to the large variability in the results.

Based on this reference-based evaluation of 23 samples, 4 samples were classified into category A, 11 samples into category B, and 12 samples into category C. The remaining 11 samples, i.e., 48%, would be classified as outside the EN 450-1 framework if this standard is used solely as a benchmark criterion. It should be noted that a large part of the samples contains carbonates (limestone), sulfates, and chlorides, which distort the final values of the LOI. If these components were considered, several samples would shift to a different classification category within this reference system, and the measured LOI values would be lower, which is important to emphasize. To verify the applicability of such biomass ashes as SCMs, an additional LOI test including these corrections would be required.

Table 4. Determination of LOI in wt.% (without correction for sulfates, chlorides, or carbonates). Values marked in red do not comply with the EN 450-1 standard.

Sample	LOI [wt.%]	Sample	LOI [wt.%]
LBP_FA_1	18.46	HO_FA_1	5.13
LBP_FA_2	14.24	HO_FA_2	7.18
LBP_FA_3	12.23	HO_FA_3	5.28
LBP_BA_1	13.86	HO_BA_1	0.42
LBP_BA_2	24.99	HO_BA_2	4.14
LBP_BA_3	1.89	HO_BA_3	4.58
JH_FA+BA_1	10.76	PO_FA_1	3.07
JH_FA+BA_2	21.13	PO_FA_2	14.50
JH_FA+BA_3	15.33	PO_FA_3	5.62
CZTL_BA_1	12.54	PO_BA_1	0.35
CZTM_BA_1	13.05	PO_BA_2	5.48
		PO_BA_3	6.56

3.3. Phase Composition (XRD)

Most samples contained a high proportion of the amorphous phase (Figures 4–9 and Table 5), which, according to XRF results, is most likely composed of aluminosilicates. Surprisingly, a small amount of the amorphous phase was found in BA samples LBP_BA_3 and PO_BA_1, which contained a high proportion of quartz at the expense of the amorphous fraction. This observation is consistent with the LOI results, in which low LOI values are associated with samples exhibiting high quartz contents. This is particularly true for sample PO_BA_1, which had the lowest LOI = 0.35 wt.% and contained 84.5 wt.% quartz. The highest proportions of the amorphous phase—which is critical for pozzolanic activity—were observed in samples from the grate combustion of pure biomass (hay + straw) at the location JH and from grate co-combustion at the locations CZTL and CZTM, reaching up to 82.2 wt.%. The samples from FBC co-combustion (locations HO and PO) showed amorphous phase proportions ranging from 6.0 to 68.2 wt.%.

Figure 4. Phase composition of input materials from grate combustion from XRD in wt.%.

Figure 5. Phase composition of input materials from grate co-combustion from XRD in wt.%.

Figure 6. Phase composition of input materials from FBC co-combustion from XRD in wt.%.

Figure 7. Diffractogram—phase composition of input materials from grate combustion. (Q = quartz, Cc = calcite, Lm = lime, An = anhydrite, Hm = hematite, Ant = anatase, P = portlandite, Mt = magnetite, Ms = muscovite, Fsp = feldspars (Ab = albite + Or = orthoclase), Ak = akermanite, Sy = sylvite, Ar = arcanite, R = rutile; CaF_2 = internal standard).

In a number of samples, regardless of the type of combustion, an increased content of calcite (CaCO_3) was detected, up to a value of 26.5 wt.% in sample LBP_BA_3. The presence of calcite in the samples can be explained by the flue gas desulfurization process [10,43–46]. Although limestone decomposes into CaO and CO_2 at high temperatures, coarse limestone particles can quickly fall through the grates into the BA. On the other hand, very fine limestone particles can quickly fly out of the boiler and get caught in the separators without decomposing. At the same time, air carbonation of the resulting ashes containing CaO may also occur. The flue gas desulfurization process also accounts for the high occurrence of free lime, which arises from the overdosing of limestone into the boilers. Free lime is

problematic from the point of view of using FA in cement or concrete (its maximum content in cement is 1.5 wt.% as specified by the EN 450-1 standard).

Figure 8. Diffractogram—phase composition of input materials from grate co-combustion. (Q = quartz, Hm = hematite, Ant = anatase, Mt = magnetite, Mu = mullite, Ab = albite, R = rutile; CaF_2 = internal standard).

Figure 9. Diffractogram—phase composition of input materials from FBC co-combustion. (Q = quartz, Cc = calcite, Lm = lime, An = anhydrite, Hm = hematite, Ant = anatase, P = portlandite, Mt = magnetite, Ms = muscovite, Fsp = feldspars (Ab = albite + Or = orthoclase), Ak = akermanite, R = rutile; CaF_2 = internal standard).

An XRD analysis of the samples revealed excessive values of CaO content in less than half of the samples. In extreme cases, such as the PO_FA_3 and PO_BA_2 samples, the free lime content was as high as 11 wt.%. However, the free lime produced in this way is so-called soft-burnt [47], and its reaction with water would be practically immediate when hydrated together with cement [48]. There is therefore no risk of delayed hydration reactions for so-called hard-burnt lime arising during the firing of clinker. Although the lime content determined through the XRD analysis is high and therefore exceeds the maximum permissible amount in cement, it can be stated that this lime is unlikely to cause delayed hydration reactions over the years. However, the hydration or slaking of lime during cement hydration is undesirable. Since this is a strongly exothermic reaction, there is an increased risk of expansion [49–51] and the formation of thermal cracks in the hardened product. Similarly, the increased amount of anhydrite or portlandite in some samples comes from the flue gas desulfurization process.

Table 5. Phase composition of input materials from XRD in wt.%. Values marked in red do not comply with the EN 450–1 standard.

Sample	Amorphous Phase	Quartz	Calcite	Lime	Anhydrite	Hematite	Anatase	Portlandite	Magnetite	Mullite	Muscovite	Albite	Orthoclase	Akermanite	Sylvite	Arcanite	Rutile	Others*
LBP_FA_1	57.1	13.6	0.0	5.7	6.0	0.6	0.0	1.2	0.1	0.0	0.6	5.3	0.4	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.1
LBP_FA_2	50.8	12.0	2.5	9.1	6.1	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.4	0.0	0.0	5.5	1.2	0.4	0.0	4.1	1.1	5.0
LBP_FA_3	38.5	27.7	1.1	5.8	6.2	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.0	14.1	2.4	3.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
LBP_BA_1	62.6	11.1	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	3.2	0.6	12.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.2
LBP_BA_2	61.2	17.7	7.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	7.6	0.7	3.2	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.4
LBP_BA_3	7.5	46.5	26.5	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3	12.4	1.9	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
JH_FA+BA_1	82.2	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.4	2.5	0.0	8.5
JH_FA+BA_2	76.3	7.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	5.0	0.0	5.4
JH_FA+BA_3	79.2	0.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.1	7.1	0.0	2.7
CZTL_BA_1	66.8	3.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.7	0.0	0.1	23.1	0.0	3.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	0.3
CZTM_BA_1	69.7	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.8	0.5	0.0	0.9	17.1	0.0	3.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6	1.3
HO_FA_1	53.2	19.1	8.1	0.5	1.7	0.1	0.1	3.0	0.2	0.0	0.7	7.7	2.0	1.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.8
HO_FA_2	42.4	20.5	3.9	5.9	7.6	0.6	0.3	0.0	0.4	0.0	1.8	12.1	2.4	2.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
HO_FA_3	45.3	20.0	5.9	4.9	8.3	0.4	0.4	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.1	6.3	2.1	3.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1
HO_BA_1	68.2	17.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.6	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.7
HO_BA_2	61.8	10.6	0.0	7.7	10.3	1.1	0.2	0.7	0.4	0.0	0.0	4.5	0.7	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
HO_BA_3	60.1	8.7	0.0	6.1	13.0	0.9	0.5	2.3	1.6	0.0	0.0	4.2	1.2	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
PO_FA_1	37.3	33.1	11.0	0.0	2.9	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.9	10.4	1.2	2.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
PO_FA_2	60.2	13.1	3.0	5.9	7.0	2.5	0.4	0.0	0.1	0.0	1.3	5.1	0.4	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
PO_FA_3	37.3	13.0	16.3	11.0	6.2	0.4	0.3	9.4	0.3	0.0	1.5	3.0	0.9	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
PO_BA_1	6.0	84.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.3	2.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
PO_BA_2	54.7	10.3	0.0	11.0	15.7	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	4.7	0.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	1.5	0.0
PO_BA_3	41.4	29.7	3.3	1.4	3.8	0.0	0.5	14.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.3	1.4	2.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

* Among others, phases that appeared in the materials rarely or in small quantities can be included (especially leucite, basanite, cristobalite, anorthoclase, wollastonite, periclase, nahcolite, anorthite, graphite, magnetite, or gypsum). In rare cases, these phases appeared in higher quantities, specifically: sample JH_FA+BA_1 contained 7.0 wt.% cristobalite; sample JH_FA+BA_2 contained 5.0 wt.% anorthite + 0.4 wt.% cristobalite; sample LBP_FA_1 contained 8.1 wt.% wollastonite; sample LBP_FA_2 contained 5.0 wt.% periclase; sample LBP_BA_1 contained 3.8 wt.% leucite + 4.3 wt.% wollastonite; and sample HO_BA_1 contained 7.8 wt.% leucite + 2.9 wt.% wollastonite.

The samples also contain phases of mica, sodium, potassium, and magnesium feldspars (muscovite, albite, orthoclase, and akermanite), which are part of the Earth's crust and often naturally accompany coal. Other minor phases include iron-bearing phases (hematite, magnetite) and titanium-bearing phases (anatase, rutile), which are also commonly found in conventional coal FA. From the perspective of the grate combustion of pure biomass (hay + straw), two additional phases—sylvite (KCl) and arcanite (K_2SO_4)—are noteworthy, as they are not typically present in conventional coal fly ash. A high proportion of sylvite, which likely originates from biomass-derived salts, was identified in samples from the JH location.

3.4. Specific Density and Specific Surface

The measured values show significant differences between individual samples, especially between FA and BA. The density of the samples ranged from 1.7672 to 2.8722 $g \cdot cm^{-3}$, reflecting the different origins and compositions of the materials. The very low density of some BA samples indicates a high porosity. The specific surface area ranged from 2880 to 7899 $cm^2 \cdot g^{-1}$. The BA and FA+BA mixture were not analyzed due to the large number of coarse fractions and significant heterogeneity. In terms of comparing locations, it can be stated that samples from the HO and PO locations have the highest density, while the JH_FA+BA mixture and BA from grate combustion and co-combustion (locations LBP and CZTL/CZTM) show lower values.

Samples from the location LBP from grate combustion have a significantly higher specific surface area compared to FBC co-combustion for FA from Hodonín (HO) and Poříčí (PO); see Table 6.

Table 6. Density and specific surface area of selected input materials.

Sample	Specific Density [$g \cdot cm^{-3}$]	Specific Surface [$cm^2 \cdot g^{-1}$]
LBP_FA_1	2.4006 ± 0.0111	7594 ± 97
LBP_FA_2	2.4176 ± 0.0166	7899 ± 279
LBP_FA_3	2.5446 ± 0.0102	7352 ± 217
LBP_BA_1	1.9458 ± 0.0022	*
LBP_BA_2	1.8233 ± 0.0053	*
LBP_BA_3	1.9944 ± 0.0006	*
JH_FA+BA_1	1.8783 ± 0.0021	*
JH_FA+BA_2	2.1044 ± 0.0017	*
JH_FA+BA_3	1.7672 ± 0.0005	*
CZTL_BA_1	2.1985 ± 0.0004	*
CZTM_BA_1	2.2166 ± 0.0021	*
HO_FA_1	2.5451 ± 0.0028	2880 ± 60
HO_FA_2	2.6044 ± 0.0030	5411 ± 105
HO_FA_3	2.7884 ± 0.0043	4563 ± 78
HO_BA_1	2.5515 ± 0.0009	*
HO_BA_2	2.8340 ± 0.0007	*
HO_BA_3	2.5708 ± 0.0016	*
PO_FA_1	2.4523 ± 0.0033	3610 ± 120
PO_FA_2	2.6696 ± 0.0063	5674 ± 215
PO_FA_3	2.8722 ± 0.0035	5054 ± 12
PO_BA_1	2.6143 ± 0.0006	*
PO_BA_2	2.6661 ± 0.0024	*
PO_BA_3	2.6295 ± 0.0006	*

* Not measured due to their coarse nature and inhomogeneity.

3.5. Particle Size Distribution (PSD)

BA and the mixture FA+BA were first sieved through a 500 µm sieve. The ratios of the oversize and undersize fractions of individual samples are shown in Table 7. As expected, the BA and mixture FA+BA samples show a significant coarseness, which is confirmed by the high proportion of an oversize fraction (>500 µm) in most samples. The exception is the HO_BA samples, which are finer than the other BA samples and contain mainly an undersize fraction (<500 µm). A relatively balanced ratio of both fractions was observed in the CZTL_BA and CZTM_BA samples. These results confirm the significant variability between individual locations and types of combustion.

Table 7. Oversize and undersize fraction on a 500 µm sieve of input BA and FA+BA materials in wt.%.

Sample	Oversize [wt.%] > 500 µm	Undersize [wt.%] < 500 µm
LBP_BA_1	78.94	21.06
LBP_BA_2	71.56	28.44
LBP_BA_3	88.08	11.92
JH_FA+BA_1	76.56	23.44
JH_FA+BA_2	77.38	22.62
JH_FA+BA_3	37.43	62.57
CZTL_BA_1	46.64	53.36
CZTM_BA_1	61.02	38.98
HO_BA_1	17.50	82.50
HO_BA_2	23.93	76.07
HO_BA_3	26.16	73.84
PO_BA_1	47.80	52.20
PO_BA_2	18.99	81.01
PO_BA_3	82.61	17.39

Table 8 presents the PSD quantiles of the undersize fraction of BA and unprocessed FA. The analysis of the PSD shows that the undersize BA samples have a significantly coarser composition than the FA samples. The coarsest fractions were detected in BA samples HO_BA and PO_BA, whose median particle size ranges from 130.2 to 393.2 µm. In contrast, FA samples HO_FA and PO_FA have a median particle size of only 15.2 to 48.0 µm, which confirms the finer nature of FA. The second coarsest group comprises samples originating from the grate combustion of pure biomass (hay + straw; JH_FA+BA), with a median particle size of 68.0–106.4 µm, together with samples CZTL ($d_{50} = 72.3$ µm) and CZTM ($d_{50} = 81.2$ µm). Samples from the location LBP exhibit similar particle size distributions for both FA and BA (with the exception of LBP_BA_3), being finer than those in the second group, yet still coarser than the FA from the locations HO and PO. An exception is sample LBP_BA_3, which has a PSD comparable to BA from the locations HO and PO and is significantly coarser than the other BA from this group. This difference is highlighted by the phase composition results, which also distinguish these samples from the rest of the LBP group, showing a predominant presence of quartz and calcite (Figure 4; Table 5).

The curves shown in Figures 10 and 11 expand the results in Table 8 and present the PSD for selected samples from each studied location. It is evident that BA samples generally have a coarser particle distribution than FA, which corresponds to the previously presented median particle size values. The HO_BA and PO_BA samples have a comparable particle size distribution curve and a relatively narrow PSD. In contrast, the HO_FA and PO_FA samples have a significantly wider PSD curve, shifted towards lower values. The JH_FA+BA and CZTL/CZTM samples have a wider particle size distribution, but it is shifted towards higher values compared to FA.

Table 8. Quantiles d10, d50, and d90 in μm of FA and undersize fraction of BA and FA+BA.

Sample	Cumulative Content [μm]		
	d10	d50	d90
LBP_FA_1	4.9	21.0	84.35
LBP_FA_2	4.9	22.9	91.6
LBP_FA_3	6.3	31.9	126.5
LBP_BA_1	5.6	37.1	112.7
LBP_BA_2	11.4	65.9	219.0
LBP_BA_3	17.0	162.8	384.1
JH_FA+BA_1	10.8	68.0	191.7
JH_FA+BA_2	20.6	106.4	318.0
JH_FA+BA_3	12.1	71.6	236.1
CZTL_BA_1	8.7	72.3	271.4
CZTM_BA_1	10.2	81.2	289.1
HO_FA_1	2.8	15.2	61.3
HO_FA_2	3.2	20.2	87.7
HO_FA_3	5.7	31.3	96.0
HO_BA_1	197.1	393.2	674.3
HO_BA_2	17.7	130.2	329.4
HO_BA_3	132.3	240.9	431.8
PO_FA_1	5.3	26.4	86.9
PO_FA_2	7.7	48.0	128.6
PO_FA_3	4.1	27.5	82.8
PO_BA_1	115.6	223.4	413.3
PO_BA_2	15.3	151.4	341.5
PO_BA_3	103.4	206.9	400.9

Figure 10. Particle size distribution curves of selected FA and undersize fraction of BA and FA+BA.

Figure 11. Cumulative particle size distribution curves of selected FA and undersize fraction of BA and FA+BA.

3.6. SEM

The SEM images show selected samples of FA, BA, or their mixtures from each location, representing the grate combustion of biomass (wood bark, hay + straw) (Figure 12), the grate co-combustion of biomass with coal (woodchips, woodchips + sawdust) (Figure 13), and the FBC co-combustion of biomass and coal (woodchips + wood bark + forest biomass residues) (Figure 14).

Samples from the grate combustion of biomass (Figure 12) from the LBP and JH locations show a high porosity, which is consistent with the results of the specific surface area determination, and irregular shapes. LBP_FA is the finest, while the LBP_BA sample is the coarsest. Furthermore, in sample JH_FA+BA, organic residues of straw and hay were identified, which corresponds to the nature of the fuel burned and is consistent with the observation reported in Wang et al., 2012 [52].

The CZTL and CZTM samples from the grate co-combustion of biomass with coal (Figure 13) are characterized by the presence of both fine and very coarse particles. The images also show that CZTL_BA is slightly more porous than CZTM_BA.

The pictures of samples from the FBC co-combustion of biomass and coal (Figure 14) show that FA (samples HO_FA and PO_FA) is significantly finer compared to BA (samples HO_BA and PO_BA). Additionally, the images show that BA exhibits a narrow particle size distribution, corroborating the conclusions drawn from the PSD analysis. The microstructure of the PO_FA sample is more porous compared to the HO_FA sample, which is consistent with the determination of the specific surface area. Furthermore, the FA samples (HO_FA and PO_FA) were found to exhibit a microstructure and particle size distribution similar to that of the LBP_FA sample.

In general, all samples from biomass combustion or co-combustion with coal exhibit a relatively porous structure compared to FA from PCC, which forms spherical sintered particles, as shown, for example, in the work of Škvára et al., 2018 [9]. Moreover, the SEM observations are in good agreement with the particle size distribution results. The finer samples correspond to FA, whereas the coarser samples correspond to BA.

Figure 12. SEM images of input materials from grate combustion (magnification 500×, 2000× and 5000×) including EDS analysis with corresponding elemental composition. (The yellow box marks the EDS analysis area, and the red font indicates values within the statistical error.)

Figure 13. SEM images of input materials from grate co-combustion (magnification 500×, 2000× and 5000×) including EDS analysis with corresponding elemental composition. (The yellow box marks the EDS analysis area, and the red font indicates values within the statistical error.)

Figure 14. SEM images of input materials from FBC co-combustion (magnification 500 \times , 2000 \times and 5000 \times) including EDS analysis with corresponding elemental composition. (The yellow box marks the EDS analysis area, and the red font indicates values within the statistical error.)

The EDS analysis shows that most of the samples exhibit an aluminosilicate character (dominance of O–Si–Al). The samples from FBC co-combustion (woodchips + wood bark + forest biomass residues) show a higher proportion of Ca, which is consistent with the explanation provided in Section 3.1 (XRF) and Section 3.3 (XRD). In the sample from the grate combustion of biomass (hay + straw; location JH), the presence of K and Cl was clearly confirmed, which corresponds to its mineralogical composition and supports the identification of sylvite (KCl). Overall, the EDS results correlate with both the chemical and phase composition.

4. Conclusions

The analyses of biomass ashes from grate and fluidized bed combustion, including co-combustion with coal, revealed a pronounced compositional variability driven by fuel mix and firing technology. All samples showed an elevated CaO, commonly accompanied by increased SO₃ and MgO; the high CaO content reflects both the biomass origin and flue gas desulfurization inputs. The fly ashes from grate combustion tended to contain more alkalis and chlorides, with the highest chloride, P₂O₅ and alkali levels observed in the hay and

straw case. Nearly half of the samples exceeded the loss on ignition (LOI) limit, especially those from the grate combustion of pure biomass or grate co-combustion. However, it is necessary to consider that, during the LOI determination according to EN 450-1, the contents of sulfates, carbonates, and chlorides were not taken into account; therefore, the corrected LOI values would be more favorable from this perspective. Most ashes contained a notable amorphous aluminosilicate fraction; co-combustion with coal increased free lime and Ca-bearing phases, while pure biomass favored salts such as sylvite and arcanite. The increased content of calcium-bearing compounds is, however, also significantly influenced by the in-boiler flue gas desulfurization process. Particle size distribution, specific surface, and SEM confirmed that biomass fly ash is consistently finer than bottom ash, which is coarse and heterogeneous—indicating that bottom and mixed ashes will likely require grinding before further use.

An important outcome of this study is the substantial temporal variability observed even in ashes originating from the same power plants and using the same combustion technology. This variability, driven by the natural fluctuations in biomass feedstock, represents a major challenge for the consistent use of biomass ash in construction materials. Consequently, such variability must be explicitly anticipated and accounted for in material qualification, mix design, and quality-control procedures.

When evaluated solely against the EN 450-1 reference framework, none of the 23 samples met the benchmark limits, a result linked not only to the combustion conditions and bottom-zone sampling, but also to the fact that they failed to meet a number of the standard's criteria. While these ashes therefore fall outside EN 450-1, they remain promising as minor additional constituents under EN 197-1 up to 5 wt.%, provided that their performance is verified on hydrated cement specimens. Targeted treatments and process adjustments could enable practical utilization, supporting circular economy goals by diverting these materials from disposal and landfilling.

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